

Rudolf Steiner and Anthroposophy: Encounters of our Spy in Leipzig, Germany, during WW1

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An Australian musician and pianist, Ethel Cooper (1871-1961), spent the duration of World War I (WW1) in Leipzig, Germany. At the outbreak of the War in 1914, she had opted not to leave Germany when that was possible. In her weekly letters (n=228) written to her sister Emmie in Adelaide, Ethel Cooper has gifted us a contemporaneous account of life in wartime Germany.

Image 1: Portrait of Ethel Cooper (image source: State Library of South Australia).

On the outbreak of the war, Ethel Cooper wrote: “On that fatal day of August 4 [1914], each man knew just where to take his stand and where he would find

the very pair of boots he required. It was a preparation so thorough and masterly, that it is a pity it was not devoted to a less devilish cause” (Register, 1921). What Ethel Cooper describes as “that fatal day” is the day Britain declared war on Germany, after Germany had declared war on Russia (1 August), on France (3 August), and invaded neutral Belgium (3 August).

As an ‘enemy alien’, Ethel Cooper was scrutinised by the civil authorities but she was never interned (she was not a male enemy alien of arms-bearing age). She recorded:

“The police came here today - they were quite civil, but forbid one to telephone in English, to speak English in the streets or to leave the town - an unnecessary precaution, for at every railway station one is obliged to show one’s pass, and every bridge and highway is guarded, so that it is impossible for a foreigner to pass” (Cooper, letter of 14 August 1914).

The sympathies of Ethel Cooper were unabashedly pro-Allies and there was no pretence otherwise. She wrote with prescience: “I can see that Germany’s enormously increasing militarism is a danger to the whole world if it is allowed to go on growing” (Cooper, letter of 15 February 1915).

Later, as the war dragged on, Ethel Cooper was refused permission to leave Germany. Finally, in the chaos of the German surrender of November 1918, she fled via the Netherlands to London. “My pass has come. - I take the next train that goes in the direction of Holland” (Cooper, letter of 1 December 1918).

Rudolf Steiner moved to Dornach, Switzerland, in 1913 (Paull, 2018a). During the war, travelling on an Austrian passport, and as a subject of a Central Power, he retained easy access to Germany (but not to Allied Power countries).

Despite the move to Dornach, throughout the war, Rudolf Steiner retained his apartment in Berlin (Paull, 2019). In 1916, he split his time evenly between Dornach and Berlin, spending six months in Berlin (January to July). During those six months of 1916 in Germany, Rudolf Steiner delivered lectures in Berlin (n=36), Bremen (n=4), Hamburg (N=2), Hannover (n=2), Kassel (n=2), Leipzig

(n=2), Munich (n=4), and Stuttgart (n=4). There was a single visit to Leipzig (21 & 22 February). The Rudolf Steiner Archives records two Leipzig lectures: 'On the Development of German Intellectual Life: A Forgotten Support for Spiritual Science Within it'; and 'The Moment of Death and the Period Thereafter'. Neither are available in English translation.

Image 2. Ethel Cooper lived at Grassstrasse 11, in Leipzig's music district (image source: limes-leipzig.de).

Ethel Cooper reported her Leipzig encounter with Rudolf Steiner:

"I have heard a couple of theosophical lectures lately - one by Dr. Steiner - the Berlin leader of the German movement, the other by Frau Wolfram, the Leipzig leader [of the Leipzig Anthroposophy Group]. Dr. Knopf has been interested in it, from the psychological viewpoint, the enormous hold these

leaders have over a large body of people. But we are rather disgusted to find how dishonest that they are in their methods, when they get on to another subject, and insist on twisting facts to suit their own theories.

Dr Steiner on 'Modern German Philosophy and War' was merely one long tirade against anybody who dared to think otherwise, and was by no means accurate in his statistics - and Frau [Elise] Wolfram on 'The Psychoanalytical Movement' left her hearers under the impression that the whole of Freud's life and work was a perverse movement for the sexual enlightenment of little children!

On Saturday Lily Braun is speaking - she is the grandchild of an illegitimate daughter of Napoleon Bonaparte, and is an excellent writer. Did you ever read her 'Memoirs of a Socialist' [Memoiren einer Sozialistin] or 'In the shadow of the Titan' [Im Schatten der Titanen]? They are really good, especially the latter - Very much love from Ethel" (Cooper, letter of 5 March 1916).

The Leipzig Theosophy branch was established in 1902. It defected to the spin-off Anthroposophy Society in 1913. It then operated until the Anthroposophy Society was banned in Germany by the Nazis in 1935. It was eventually re-established after the fall of the Berlin Wall (in 1989) (Wolfram-Zweig, 2015). (Under the post WW2 partition, Leipzig was in East Germany). Lily Braun [1865-1916] was a German feminist and socialist. Her books do not appear to have been translated into English (1909a, 1909b).

The text of Rudolf Steiner's Leipzig lectures was not located, but we know that his WW1 lectures were tailored for a German audience, and would quite likely have raised the hackles of others. For example, Rudolf Steiner told a Berlin audience that: "I have tried to find a succinct formulation for the feelings different nations may be seen to have towards war, saying that a Russian believes he is going to war for the sake of religion, an Englishman for competition, a Frenchman for the glory, an Italian or Spaniard for his homeland and a German to fight for existence. And we are therefore able to say that ...

the Englishman takes action and does business ... the German aspires" (Steiner, 1914).

In WW1, some Anthroposophists took an unequivocal pacifist stance, but that was not a position adopted by Rudolf Steiner. The British Anthroposophist and translator of Rudolf Steiner, George Kaufmann, served gaol time in Britain as a draft resister. The Italian fashionista and Anthroposophist, Rosa Genoni, represented Italy at the Women's Peace Congress of 1915 at the Hague (Paull, 2018b). The Italian-Australian artist, and Anthroposophist, Ernesto Genoni, volunteered in the Australian Army (AIF) and served as a stretcher bearer on the Somme, then, when he was conscripted into the Italian Army, he refused to take the Italian oath of allegiance, he was court martialled, and he served time in military gaols in Italy (Paull, 2014).

Ethel Cooper related her experience of a theosophist visitor:

"Dr Knopf comes as usual on Wednesday and Saturday evenings, and as usual we fight over politics, and then read philosophy, being at present deep in [Nobel Prize for Literature laureate, Dr Rudolf Christoph] Eucken [1846-1926], the Jena professor, and his theories of the soul-life. Telemaque and his wife have a Frau Meyer staying with them, from Bremen. She is an ardent theosophist, and I pity the poor woman, for I never heard a human being teased so unmercifully as Telemaque teases her. She is not particularly clever in defending her standpoint, and one is simply driven to help her. But dishonestly of that sort brings its own judgement, and the judgement upon me, in this instance, has taken the form of a mass of theosophic literature which Frau Meyer now brings me! She says I am very near the realisation of the higher truth, and if I could only read this and that I shall see clearly! Nora would smile though if she could sometimes hear me standing up for poor Frau Meyer against Telemaque's cold-blooded materialism" (Cooper, letter of 8 August 1915).

Ethel Cooper was denounced by neighbours as a spy on multiple occasions. There were raids on her home. She relates one occasion:

“It turned out to be a denunciation against me for spying in the lazarettes [war-wounded hospitals]. I was angry - I have learned though how to deal with the German official so I banged with my fist on the table in the approved manner, and rolled out the titles of all the people who asked me to go to the hospitals - Herr Professor this and Frau Geheimrat [Privy Councillor] that, and Frau Reichsgerichtsrat [Imperial Judge] the other. The titles worked wonders ... they had the coolness to say that they had nothing against my continuing my charitable work ... I am glad to have got to know those hospitals so well and I like the common soldiers. They are in a tragic situation and they feel it.

I am sure they are using the Cyan Rali bombs [chemical weapons] for we hear of terrible Russian losses this week, and the Russians are mown down before they get within shot of the Germans - that can only be through the bombs. I suppose they are using them for the Zeppelin raids too” (Cooper, letter of 2 April 1916).

Civilian life was difficult during the war. The British blockaded Germany, from the outset, with the objective of denying supplies to the enemy (Bell, 1937). Ethel Cooper wrote of her frustration that: “The whole day goes in the search for what is necessary to live on just for that day” (letter of 19 August 1917). She took the pragmatic view: “where everything is forbidden, you simply have to break the law” (Cooper, letter of 4 August 1918).

It is not proved that Ethel Cooper was a spy. Her raison d'être for being in Leipzig was music. In the course of the war she was scrutinised by the authorities but her secrets were never discovered. Her clandestine night visit to military barracks, and her forbidden visits to the countryside, were not detected. She travelled on public transport to eavesdrop conversations. She visited interned Allied POWs, she had access to English newspapers (Register, 1921), she successfully smuggled letters out of Germany, and her cache of letters to her sister, Emmie, were never discovered. “Also, she was able to assist the American Consul, for, after all those years abroad, the German language came as readily as her own” (Register, 1921). She wrote to her sister: “Whether they

have a suspicion of the other thing I can't say" (letter of 22 April 1917) and "I am convinced they have nothing really against me" (Cooper, letter of 20 May 1917).

After the war, Ethel Cooper served with the Quaker Relief Effort in Poland (as did the British Anthroposophist George Kaufmann). "Miss Ethel Cooper ... is in charge of relief work for the Society of Friends in Poland" (Advertiser, 1922). She related the situation in Poland: "The people are absolutely destitute. They have come back, after years of war, to find their houses burnt, they have literally no possessions at all. We ... are feeding all we can" (Macleay Chronicle, 1923).

Ethel Cooper finally returned to her hometown of Adelaide (in 1936) - the city where she had begun her musical career and where she had given concert performances (e.g. Advertiser, 1908; Register, 1907, 1909). She had been lauded: "Miss Cooper is one of the most accomplished pianists that the Conservatorium of Music has trained " (Advertiser, 1908). However, after the war, she reportedly "never again played the piano" (Cooper, 1982, p.15). She lamented: "Music, the great love of my life, appears to have deserted me" (Register, 1921).

Ethel Cooper described herself as "a happy vagabond" (News, 1932). She declared: "I was a strange wild creature that careered over the world defying every one of its laws of decency and good upbringing" (Register, 1911). She has left us with her own week-by-week eye-witness chronicle of history-in-the-making, which relates her frank and forthright testimony of the vagaries of civilian life in war-time Germany, including her passing encounters with Anthroposophy.

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